

THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF THE INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REGION INDUSTRY

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Abstract

The article outlines the theoretical aspects of the innovative development of the region's industry in the eyes of various scientists. Analyzed are several systems focused on effective product production technology. The reasons for the need for innovative development of the regional industry are listed one by one. Instead, there are ways to activate the transfer of technology among industrial sectors and to properly use elements of innovative infrastructure.

Keywords: theory, system, technological policy, process technologies, classroom, region, industry, innovation, innovative approach, innovative park, innovative infrastructure.

Introduction

The region can also be analyzed as an independent economic entity. Analysis of factors that determine the growth of the region's economy shows that regions are the pillars of the country's economy development. The transition of the country's economy to an innovative path is considered an important issue, while the industry of the region and its innovative development act as an impulse.

In modern times, the "regionalization" of innovative politics is linked to the innovative development of the world economy. Jehovah's Witnesses would be pleased to discuss these protracts.

In this case, a special aspect of technological and innovative policy is that the effort to implement "process technologies" is intensifying in order to reduce costs.

The present period is a period of non-standardization aimed at scientific production, based not on production and sales volumes, but on a system that constantly updates products aimed at "product (efficient) technology" (importing new goods into the market, regularly updating). In this case, small and medium-sized enterprises, not large enterprises, will now take the lead in the region. They are characterized by faster flexibility in changing product technology and the production of competitive products in small capital

investment. As a result, many enterprises within the region specialize in the production of raw materials and equipment related to a particular industrial sector. This reduces the cost of introducing new technologies into the region and increases gross commercial efficiency. Therefore, specialization is carried out within a specific industrial network.

The introduction of innovation into the regional industry is also becoming a necessity for the following reasons:

- deepening the natural resource deficit and regularly increasing their prices;
- cultural development, namely, the growth and complexity of consumer, social and ecological standards in industrial production;
- increased competition, i.e. the need to constantly increase the efficiency of industrial production, and the identification and cost of individual types of resources;
- an increase in the quality and technological parameters of manufactured goods.

Literature analysis

Studies have shown that innovative development of the regional industry is primarily influenced by external and internal factors, which are divided into four groups: economic, technological, social and political. In their research, scientists such as S.Yu.Glazev, R.S.Greenberg, A.I.Tatarkin, who conducted scientific research in the field of regional industrial development, emphasized that innovation is a key factor in the intensive development of the region's industrial complex. Factors that influence progress in this direction are systemation factors that divide them into external and internal factors.

In his work, Mr. Porter says that "everyone wants to be the best, but you have to be unique. " Uniqueness allows you to ensure superiority in competition as well as a high profit standard. Also, A.Y.Prikhacha believed that "the effectiveness of the innovative process is much higher than the standard approach and technique, and innovation in achieving high efficiency should be such an idea that its implementation will allow you to make a large amount of profit, strengthen investment flow and increase industrial production volumes." L.M. Chistov, on the other hand, divided the innovative development of industry into three categories of revolution (increasing the efficiency of industrial production by 20% or more annually), medium (10%20%) and low (1-10%).

According to S. Kochetkov, innovative potential refers to the overall ability of existing resources to achieve innovative goals. Such resources include personnel, production and investment resources. When it comes to innovative potential in A. Nikolaeva's work, it is understood that the system of factors and conditions necessary for the implementation of innovative processes is understood. Based on an assessment of the state of innovative potential lies the region's own state of innovative opportunity. In the work of V.N.Gunin, V.P.Baranchev, N.P.Maslennikova, V.M.Mishin, the concept of innovative potential will be evaluated from the point of view of a systematic approach. At the same time, the region's readiness for sustainable industrial production and innovation will be taken into account. Of course, evaluation of the possibility of innovative resources is necessary in the early stages of regional development.

German researcher G. Mensh believes that in times of depression, the economy's tendency to intensify innovation would be highest. Depression will force one to look for opportunities to 'survive', which will serve to overcome innovation processes. Mensh called it a 'trigetric effect of depression'. He emphasizes that the innovation process should not be at the same margin, this will lead to the emergence of innovative classrooms, and the role of the state in the innovative development of the regional industry will be of particular importance. In order for the state to successfully implement innovation policies and classification processes in the region, it must support strengthening the innovation process in a timely manner and be able to anticipate the time when it can produce synergetic results. This is because delayed government assistance could lead to a decrease in the efficiency of innovation.

The need to develop industrial clusters in the innovative development of the regional industry can also be found in M. Porter's work⁸. He believes that industrial enterprises should maintain their productivity at a high level only by regularly creating inventions and introducing innovation.

According to Mr. Porter's theory of an industrial cluster, the geographically close location of companies operating in a particular industry network allows regions to create a competitive advantage. By Porter, the cluster is "a group of mutually exclusive companies and related organizations that operate in a particular area and are characterized by the generality of their activities and complement each other." The development of the regional industry was further developed by the cluster theory M. Enright. He believes that the historical framework for the development of regional industry, the diversity of business culture, and the organization of production are important. In his work, he

emphasizes classrooms in the innovative development of the regional industry, describing industrial clusters as geographically closely interconnected by member firms and agglomeration of interconnected industries.

The integration and systematization of existing approaches has enabled the region to develop a classification of factors that affect the innovative development of industrial production, taking into account all available factors. This systematizing has enabled us to confirm that innovation is the most important of them and has a comprehensive impact on the industrial foundation.

Results and discussion

It is difficult to develop an innovative model of industry without the efficient use of economic advantages. The main pillar of the innovative development of the regional industrial complex is the development of industrial and technological levels, the use of innovation in the formation of a technological chain, the strengthening of integration within mutual sectors, the deepening of industrial and commercial specialization, and the formation of industrial clusters.

So there are several types of innovative infrastructure formation. At the same time, the formation of scientific parks, research parks, incubators, innovation centers, techno parks, and classrooms as a result of industrial production and the integration of science is one of the most important steps in this direction. In most cases, these objects reflect a large-scale scientific and industrial complex, covering all stages of innovative processes. The scientific park is an integrated form of science and industry, while the research park is a collection of nonprofit research institutes with close ties to the industry.

Innovative centers, on the other hand, are responsible for integrating ideas with capital and entrepreneurs and helping innovative companies attract financial assets in the initial phase of their work. Technological parks, on the other hand, are an organization that promotes the development of a regional innovative environment and is organized to support the independent work of small innovative companies and organizations that implement scientific and technological advances in industrial production in order to develop business in the scientific and technological field by establishing a material and technological base.

Technological parks can be organized in the form of innovative industrial clusters. Classrooms are one of the most effective methods of innovative development of the regional industry. Their organization will increase the innovative activity of all participants in the association. But the establishment of

production clusters does not provide for the compulsory introduction of ITTKIs. The cluster approach is one of the most effective tools of regional industrial policy around the world. The activities of implementing a cluster approach are called clustering and represent a collection of a number of organizational and economic activities. Of course, these events should be carried out by government and society institutions in order to integrate enterprises into classrooms and establish informal relations between them.

Examples of such industrial clusters include Basel, Switzerland, Leverkusen, Frankfurt-Maine, and Lyuvigshafen, along the Rhine River in Germany.

The experience of many of the above countries suggests that there is no single mechanism for organizing, developing and encouraging classrooms. Based on this approach, to modernize the region's economy, it is necessary to develop a valid class policy program that will support the initiatives of representatives of industrial complexes in modern economic and social conditions. It is possible to specify several possible approaches to support the development of clusters.

The formation of clusters is a long enough process (Silicon Valley began to form as a cluster in the 1940s) and required a lot of effort from industrial complexes, government and governing bodies, as well as representatives of small and medium-sized businesses.

Showing international experience in the formation of clusters (e.g. Chinese experience in the formation of automobile clusters), industrial zones consisting of one or more large enterprises should first be established in the region. This provides a certain basis for the production of auxiliary products and the development of infrastructure. This is an important point of the process and the development of personnel capacity through the involvement of highly qualified personnel.

This will manage the period from the production of a new product to the process of selling it on the market. The created conditions will attract large and medium-sized businesses to the region, activate activities to establish new companies, and develop small businesses. The development of an effective program for the establishment of a cluster system after the establishment of an industrial-economic complex will lead to an increase in the efficiency of the industrial complex by activating industrial activity in the region.

Conclusions

Therefore, the combination of experience, labor, skills, technology, technology, energy, and raw materials is the driving force of innovative

potential. The following factors should be considered in the innovative development of the regional industry:

- the participation of the state in innovative processes;
- the level of competitiveness of technology in world markets;
- the level of informability of innovative processes;
- innovative infrastructure;
- the level of integration of science and production;
- ensuring the regulatory and legal environment;
- the level of socio-economic development of socio-economic networks.

Instead, it is a method of effectively implementing the innovative potential of the regional industry, primarily the activation of the transfer of mutual technology among industrial sectors and the proper use of elements of innovative infrastructure. Innovative development of industry is a key factor in the development of the economy. Modernizing production, mastering high-tech technologies, and ensuring its transparency by reducing resource identification will lead to the maintenance of industrial enterprises without harm. This allows to financially facilitate the process of organizing clusters, establishing free economic zones, scientific parks, commercial incubators, technoparks.

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